

Household Survey on Food Behaviors and Nutrition Status in Suburb of Thailand

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Abstract : This household survey aimed to describe food behaviors and nutritional status of households in suburb nearby Bangkok, Thailand. Through convenience sampling, sample included 187 food providers from 125 households in three communities. Data were collected by structured interview and nutritional assessment. Results revealed that majority of the sample were female (68.4 %), aged between 18 to 91 years. The households selected raw foods concerning quality as the first priority (46.5%), cooking for their family members as 91.2%, using seasonings as 71.2%. The most favorite tastes were sweet (19.8%), salty (20.3%), and fatty (1.6%). Food related health problems were hypertension (40.1%), diabetes (26.7%), and dyslipidemia (19.3%). Approximately half of the overall samples (55.1%) and the sample with hypertension (84.5%) had excessive body mass index (BMI). Moreover, one-fourth of the sample with hypertension (25.3%) had salty food preference. Results suggest approaches to promote behavioral modification for sodium reduction particularly in food providers of households with hypertension and excessive BMI.

Keywords : food behavior, nutrition status, household, suburb

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